

Risk and Retribution: How Punishment Uncertainty Weakens Norms of Cooperation

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Abstract

Studies have demonstrated that certain sanctioning institutions can play an essential role in maintaining human cooperation in public goods experiments. However, in reality, the outcome of sanctions can be subject to stochasticity. In a public goods experiment with peer punishment, we investigated the comparative advantage of certain versus uncertain sanctioning institutions by allowing participants to repeatedly choose between the two. In one institution, sanctions issued by individuals were multiplied by three, while in another, the consequences of sanctions were multiplied by a random factor between 0 and 6. Initially, the uncertain institution was the majority choice, but it eventually tended to become the minority choice. We found less punishment, due to less antisocial punishment, in a certain institution, leading to higher contributions and payoffs. Hence, when participants learned about the difference in payoffs, they chose a certain sanctioning institution more often. Especially, prosocial and risk-averse individuals with strong contribution norms were more likely to choose certainty. Additionally, we investigated the motives that may influence pro- and antisocial punishment, as they influence an institution's success. We find that hypersensitivity to punishment, non-prosocial punishment motives, weak contribution norms, and normative hubris reduce the effectiveness of sanctions in establishing cooperation.

Introduction

From environmental preservation to the maintenance of common resources, individuals need to cooperate to provide public goods [1]. Yet, cooperation is against individuals' self-interest, and maintaining it requires keeping individual selfishness in check [2, 1]. Past work has shown that sanctioning institutions play an essential role in maintaining

cooperative behavior in human groups [3, 4, 5, 6, 7]. For instance, in public-good experiments, once humans are provided with a sanctioning institution allowing them to sanction others at a personal cost, they are willing to use sanctioning means to establish a prosocial order [5, 4, 8, 3]. Furthermore, past work has shown that when humans are offered a choice between a sanctioning and a sanction-free institution, they are likely to choose the sanctioning institution, once they learn about the contribution-enhancing function of such institutions [9, 10]. Such observations suggest that sanctioning institutions can offer advantages in maintaining social order, and may have been selected in an evolutionary process [11]. Theoretical work, using evolutionary models, has shown how this selection can occur in an evolutionary process [6].

However, the use of sanctioning as a means to establish prosocial order is by no means guaranteed. Imposing sanctions on others to promote prosocial behavior requires individuals to expend personal resources such as time, effort, or money. As such, sanctioning institutions are a public good and vulnerable to free-riding, a point that is usually referred to as the second-order free-rider problem [12, 13, 6]. Moreover, a common observation in public goods experiments is antisocial punishment, whereby individuals use sanctioning as a means to punish those who behave prosocially [14, 15, 16]. Theoretical work has shown that antisocial punishment can be a problem for the evolution and effectiveness of sanctioning institutions [17, 18], and empirical work has demonstrated that antisocial punishment is rather ubiquitous [16]. Given the central role of sanctioning institutions in maintaining cooperative behavior, these observations necessitate a better understanding of humans' motivation and preferences for using sanctioning, as well as the external and structural factors that can affect humans' ability to use these institutional means for promoting cooperative behavior.

Uncertain sanctioning institutions

We begin with a simple observation: most of the past work on the role of punishment in promoting cooperative behavior has focused on an idealized situation in which the consequences of sanctions are certain [5, 4, 8, 3]. This contrasts with real-world situations in which the causes and consequences of sanctions are subject to considerable uncertainty. In real-world situations, for instance, the cost of the same punitive action, such as a fight or ostracisation, can vary from an inconsequential outcome to death. Similarly, legal punishment is generally subject to uncertainty due to individual factors affecting the decision: Subjective assessment [19], or even the outcome of last night's sports game [20], or whether judging is done before or after lunch [21], can affect judges' decisions. Furthermore, the degree to which the rule of law is enforced varies around the world, introducing additional uncertainty about fair legal treatment, which has been demonstrated to affect individual cooperation and punishment behavior [16].

Recently, such stochasticities have been shown to have substantial consequences for human punishment behavior, so some of the insights gained from studies in idealized, certain situations may not hold in such uncertain institutions [22]. For instance, uncertainty about punishment outcomes is found to reduce cooperation and prosocial punishment while increasing antisocial punishment [22]. These observations raise the question of how

certain and uncertain sanctioning institutions perform when competing with one another and of how the opportunity to choose between them affects cooperative and punitive behavior. Allowing individuals to choose between different collective action settings, such as institutions or public goods that differ in terms of reliability, cost or return, has been shown to promote cooperation and reflects many real-world situations in which individuals select between groups, organizations or communities that offer different cooperative environments [23, 24]. Individuals often have to choose between institutions that differ in how reliably or transparently sanctions are applied. Citizens can, for instance, choose to resolve disputes through state courts, which apply formal and predictable penalties, or through informal or community-based systems where outcomes are more uncertain. Similarly, organizations and firms vary in the clarity of their disciplinary procedures, leading employees to self-select into workplaces with more or less predictable enforcement. Online communities provide another example: users can join platforms with strict and transparent moderation policies or those with inconsistent rule enforcement. These contexts all feature endogenous institutional choice under differing levels of sanction certainty, paralleling the structure of our experimental setting.

Although certain sanctioning institutions may prove beneficial for social welfare, we suggest that the propensity to prefer them over uncertain institutions may be subject to individual preferences. Individuals with higher prosocial preferences are stronger cooperators and show an increased willingness to enforce cooperation through prosocial punishment [25, 26]. This makes them strong candidates for preferring certain sanctioning institutions that ensure that prosocial sanctions work as intended. Selfish individuals who wish to free-ride, on the other hand, may seek refuge in uncertain sanctioning institutions that jeopardise the norm of prosocial punishment. Preference for a certain sanctioning institution may depend not only on prosociality, but also on individuals' risk preferences. Risk-seeking individuals show more cooperation in social dilemmas where cooperation is risky [27, 28], a phenomenon attributed to them relying less on previous cooperative signals [29]. Also, risk-seeking individuals may prefer an uncertain institution where variability in sanction multipliers increases the expected magnitude of both issued and received punishments. They may also perceive it as fostering a more cooperative environment, since higher potential punishments could act as stronger deterrents to free-riding.

Here, we present the results of a public goods experiment in which participants repeatedly choose the sanctioning institution in which to participate. In each round, subjects chose how much to contribute to the public good, and then received information about the contributions and incomes of all players in their group. In the certain sanctioning institution, the number of monetary units (MU) spent to punish others was tripled on the way to the receiver. In the uncertain sanctioning institution, the MU spent on punishment was multiplied by a randomly drawn number between 0 and 6 to determine the fine issued. In accordance with our preregistered hypotheses (<https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/7HYBW>), we found lower punishment, and a lower fraction of antisocial punishment, in the certain institution, leading to higher contributions and payoffs. These factors lead to a higher attractiveness of the certain institution,

such that, as participants learn about the payoffs of the two institutions, they immigrate to the certain sanctioning institution. Individuals who acted more prosocially or risk-averse in incentivized post-experiment tasks chose the certain institution more often.

Perception, motivation of sanctions, and personal contribution norms

Past work in public goods experiments has shown that humans' perceptions of their environment have a crucial impact on their contribution decisions. For instance, framing of the same cooperative game in a more cooperative or competitive language that changes human perception of the game can lead to dramatically different behavior [30], in a way that shows variation across subjects [31]. However, while much is known about the external causes and consequences of punishment, little is known about its internal causes and motivations.

Past work on the motivation for prosocial punishment has pointed to strong reciprocity [32] (according to which humans are strong reciprocators who cooperate and punish uncooperative behavior), inequity aversion [33, 34], revenge [35], status-seeking [36], or anticipated satisfaction [37].

Similarly, while the existence of antisocial punishment has been repeatedly demonstrated in previous research [14, 15, 16], its underlying causes at the individual level remain unclear. Structural explanations for antisocial punishment have included norms of civic cooperation and the weak rule of law [16]. Antisocial punishment has been shown not to be due to aversion to inequality [38], but to be targeted at those who violate descriptive norms [39], and has been argued to be the result of status-seeking [40], or revengeful acts [41]. Other research has established a link between antisocial punishment and psychophysiological factors [42], or dark personality traits [43, 44, 45].

Here we ask how humans' perceptions of their environment affect their sanctioning behavior, whether meaningful differences exist among subjects in the way that they perceive and represent their own and others' behavior, and if so, how such psychological factors affect cooperative and sanctioning behavior. To do so, we rely on quantitative post-experiment survey measures to infer participants' perceptions of their behavior and environment, allowing us to relate their perceptions to their actual behavior, and thus to address how their perceptions may shape their behavior. Since these measures were administered after the public goods game, the results may reflect participants' experiences during the game. Therefore, these associations should be interpreted as correlational. This contrasts with previous research that has relied on indirect manipulation of circumstances to induce antisocial punishment. Our approach allows us to examine three further potential pathways that motivate punishment, undermine the norm of prosocial punishment, and drive antisocial punishment.

First, we examine how participants' perceptions of the punishments they issued and received relate to their actual behavior. By comparing perceived and actual punishments, we can test whether individuals misperceive their own and others' sanctioning behavior in ways that maintain a positive self-image, even when they do not contribute or engage in retaliation. After the game, participants estimated the average amount of punishment they believed they had imposed and received. Many participants described

their punishments as prosocial, even when they did not primarily target free-riders. This indicates a self-enhancing bias in how individuals recall and justify their actions. Participants who believed they had received more punishment than they actually did also tended to punish more severely, especially in an antisocial manner. These patterns suggest that anger and revenge may drive antisocial punishment [41]; however, such motives are filtered through subjective perceptions of fairness, which allow individuals to maintain a prosocial self-image.

Second, we examine how different types of punishment motivation are related to sanctioning behavior. We asked the subjects what their rationale was for imposing punishment. This allows us to distinguish between subjects who punish out of inequity aversion (prosocial punishment motivation) and those who punish for other reasons (non-specific punishment motivation). We find that, while a higher proportion of punishment issued by individuals with prosocial motivations is prosocial, these individuals punish less overall than those with non-specific punishment motivation.

Finally, we explore the whether personal contribution norms, i.e., the level of contributions individuals consider appropriate, guide individuals' contribution and sanctioning decisions. We expect strong contribution norms to be associated with more cooperation and a willingness to enforce cooperation through prosocial punishment, as well as an ensuing preference for the more effective sanctioning institution. We are also interested in finding out whether deviating from one's own contribution norm affects the choice of punishment. We find that while norm-adherents prefer certainty, they do not differ in their choice of prosocial punishment, while those who transgress from their own contribution norm punish more antisocially.

Results

Competitive advantage of certain sanctioning institutions

In Fig. 1 we present the proportion of subjects choosing the uncertain institution as a function of game rounds. The result shows an identifiable trend: while at the beginning of the experiment we do not see any significant deviation from the institutions being chosen with equal frequency, more subjects learn to switch to the certain sanctioning institution as the experiment progresses. While 51.8% of the subjects chose the uncertain institution in the first round, only 40.8% did so in the final round. A logistic regression model estimating the effect of round number on institution choice shows that the odds of choosing the uncertain institution decrease by 1.09% ($p < 0.05$) for each additional round played.

Fig. 2 presents the per round means of four indicators of competitive advantage as estimated by multi-level regression models (Figure S1 in the SI summarizes the models' regression coefficients; figure S3 in the SI shows the uncorrected per round means; models are described in more detail in the methods section). In the certain institution, the estimated mean round contribution is 6.40 MU, or 8.8% higher, compared to 5.88 in the uncertain institution ($p < 0.001$). In addition, according to the model, players in the

certain institution are estimated to spend on average 0.22 MU less on punishing others, which equals a reduction of 20.5% ($p < 0.001$). This difference between institutions is in part due to the fact that players in the certain institution use antisocial punishment less, as they are estimated to use only 0.31 MU per round to punish other players who contribute less than they do. In contrast, in the uncertain institution players are estimated to spend 0.42 MU or 35.5% more on antisocial punishment ($p < 0.001$). As a result of higher contributions and lower expenses to punish others, subjects in the certain institution are estimated to earn per round more than three times the MU with 4.81 compared to only 1.6 MU in the uncertain institution ($p < 0.001$). The reduced round performance in the uncertain institution condenses into impaired earnings for subjects who choose it more frequently: The fraction of decisions in which the uncertain institution was chosen negatively affects the final balance of MU at the end of the game. Subjects who exclusively chose the uncertain institution a decrease in the final balance by 92.38 MU compared to those who exclusively chose the certain institution. To account for learning effects, we reran the regression models, restricting them to the final 15 rounds as a robustness check. We found no difference in the direction or significance of the effects (see SI figure 2).

These findings speak for an competitive advantage of the certain sanctioning institution in generating social welfare. As uncertainty hampers the effectiveness of punishment in the uncertain institution, even higher punishments fail to maintain cooperation levels in sum leading to lower payoffs. A reason for the ineffectiveness of punishment payments may lie in punishment payments losing their purpose as a means of sanctioning in the uncertain institution. While in the certain institution receiving a higher penalty in a previous round is associated with an increase in contribution, being penalized has no effect on contributions in the uncertain institution (see SI figure S4). On the other hand, punishment received in the previous round increases issued punishment in the uncertain institution more than in the certain institution (see SI figure S5). Therefore, punishment payments appear as a means of expressing spite instead of a tool to enforce cooperation in the uncertain institution.

Another approach to explain the superiority of certain punishments is to look at which individuals choose each institution. If the individual characteristics of the players in each institution differ, and are associated with different behavior, this would explain some of the differences. Accordingly, we find that participants' choices are correlated with their risk attitudes. To see this, we examine the relationship between participants' behavior in the public good game and their risk attitude as measured by a staircase risk survey [46]. In this survey, participants are presented with five choices between a certain payment and a lottery, starting with a certain payment option equal to the expected value of the lottery. For each choice of sure payment, the sure payment in the next decision decreases and vice versa, so that in the end the subject's expected utility is obtained.

Figure 3A shows the estimated probability of choosing the uncertain institution as a function of individual risk preferences. Regression results yield an odds ratio of 1.043 ($p < 0.001$) for each additional MU of expected lottery utility. While individuals with the

lowest risk preference are estimated to choose the uncertain institution only 36% of the time, this number increases to 67% for individuals with the highest risk preference. Figure 3C depicts random effects linear regression coefficients for the relationship between risk seeking and game behavior. Higher risk preference is associated with increased punishment payments (0.014; $p < 0.001$), but is unrelated to contribution (0.001; $p > 0.05$) or antisocial punishment (0.001, $p > 0.05$). This indicates risk-seeking may be an underlying factor of using sanctioning means to establish a prosocial order.

On the other hand, social preferences have an inverse relationship with the choice of institution compared to risk preferences, as shown in Figure 3B. Participants completed a Social Value Orientation (SVO) assessment in which they divided payoffs between themselves and a randomly selected study participant across 15 decisions. This yielded an SVO angle, which measures their prosociality [47]. Regression results indicate that the odds of an uncertain institution choice decrease by an odds ratio of 0.984 ($p < 0.001$) for each additional degree of the resulting SVO angle. Estimated probabilities of uncertain institution choice range from 67% for the least prosocial to 40% for the most prosocial. Figure 3D shows random effects linear regression coefficients for the relationship between social value orientation and behavior. Larger social value orientation angle relates to increased game contributions (0.01; $p < 0.01$) and overall punishment (0.004; $p < 0.005$), but not antisocial punishment (0.0002; $p > 0.05$). Overall, individual preferences may attenuate the adoption of the certain institution, as prosocials may remain in the uncertain institution to better be able to free-ride, and risk-seekers may prefer its stochastic punishment.

Exploratory Analysis: The role of perception, motivation and norms in shaping cooperative and sanctioning behavior

An important question is how the perception of their environment shapes individuals' contribution and punishment decisions. To address this question, we included post-experiment survey questions asking participants to estimate their average contribution, the average punishment they issued, and the average punishment they received. The distribution of the delta between subjects' perceptions of their contribution and received and issued punishment and their actual contribution and punishment is shown in SI Figures S6 to S9. Subjects have a fairly realistic perception of the punishment they impose on others, with a mean delta (0.05) that is not significantly different from 0 ($p=0.85$). In contrast, the distribution of the delta between the perceived and actual punishment which they receive is strongly skewed to the left, indicating that subjects collectively underestimate the punishment they receive (by an average of 2.18MU; $p = 0.011$). Contributions show the opposite trend: subjects tend to perceive their contribution to be higher than what it actually was (on average 0.21MU, $p=0.059$). Looking at the distribution of the deviation of the subjects' mean contribution from their self-reported contribution norm of how much they think was an appropriate contribution shows that most subjects contribute below their own contribution norm (on average 2.68 MU less; $p = 0.009$). These results suggest that, collectively, subjects exhibit a self-serving bias with respect to the perception of their environment.

To assess the impact of perception on behavior, we first look at participants' perceptions of how much punishment they issued to or received from other subjects. Figure 4A depicts multilevel linear regression estimates of the relationship of subjects own perceived punishing behavior on the actual punishment they issued. The perceived MU paid for punishment shows a strong but far from perfect correlation with actual mean punishment (0.44; $p < 0.001$). Controlling for actual punishing behavior, perceived punishment shows a positive effect on contributions (0.058; $p < 0.001$), a negative effect on antisocial punishment (-0.013 ; $p < 0.001$), while increasing prosocial punishment (0.008; $p = 0.001$). These findings may suggest that a superiority bias is at work in the way subjects represent and remember their own sanctioning behavior, such that prosocial behavior leaves a more salient trace of their perception of their own behavior.

Figure 4 B shows the multilevel linear regression results of how subjects' perception of punishment received is related to their punishment and cooperative behavior. Controlling for the actual punishment subjects received, subjects' higher perception of received punishment decreased contribution (-0.054 ; $p < 0.001$) and significantly increased overall punishment (0.018; $p < 0.001$), antisocial punishment (0.004; $p < 0.001$), and prosocial punishment (0.003; $p < 0.001$). This finding suggests that while punishment behavior may be motivated by revenge, these motivations are mediated by individuals' perceptions of their social environment and do not necessarily correspond to objective realities. Furthermore, the fact that free-riding and the perception of received (and issued) punishment are correlated, suggests that free-riders have a more negative perception of their environment.

Another factor influencing the use of punishment is the motivation underlying punishment. Subjects with a prosocial punishment motivation (who showed high agreement with the statement that they punished free-riders) use punishment mainly on free-riders, likely as a tool to enforce the norm of cooperation. Contrary, those with no specific punishment motivation rank high on all means of using punishment and may use the opportunity to satisfy other needs. Figure 4C shows the mean and median MU spent for total, prosocial, and antisocial punishment by punishment motivation. On average, subjects with prosocial punishment motivation punish 0.54 MU, or less than half, per player per round compared to 1.27 MU for those with non-specific punishment motivation. This difference is partly explained by the discrepancy in antisocial punishment between the motivations, which is more than twice as high with 0.44 MU per player and round for subjects with non-specific motivation compared to the 0.19 MU of those with prosocial punishment motivation. Subjects with prosocial punishment motivation also pay less (0.25MU) towards prosocial punishment compared to subjects without a specific punishment motivation (0.65MU). For both groups, prosocial punishment makes up around half of all punishment payments. While it may seem that subjects with a prosocial punishment motivation should prefer the certain punishment institution due to its advantage in enforcing cooperation, we do not find significant differences in institution choice between punishment motivations (see figure S10 in the SI).

Finally, we look at subjects' individual contribution norms, as subjects who perceive contribution as an obligation may be more inclined to use punishment to enforce con-

tributions. Clearly, the participants norms can be highly correlated with their actual behavior. To control for this correlation, in Figure 4D we plot the random effects linear regression coefficients of both contribution norm and the delta between contribution norm and actual contribution, which we call normative hubris. While the former does not control for the subjects actual behavior, the latter does.

For each MU increase in personal contribution norm, punishment decreases by 0.13 MU and antisocial punishment decreases by 0.09 MU (both $p < 0.001$). Contribution norm, however, is unrelated to prosocial punishment ($0.001; p = 0.13$). This is consistent with the unexpected finding that prosocial punishment is unrelated to prosocial behavior (contribution to public goods) [48, 49]. This finding is in contradiction with some of the theories explaining prosocial punishment, namely strong reciprocation [49]. Not surprisingly, increases in the contribution norm are also strongly related to increases in contribution behavior ($0.53; p < 0.001$).

Controlling for subjects' actual contribution allows us to investigate the role of normative hubris i.e., cases when a subject's contribution norms surpasses their own contributions. Random effects linear regression results show that for each MU by which subjects' contribution norm is above their actual contribution, the MU they spent for punishment increase by 0.007 ($p < 0.01$). This is explained by an increase in antisocial punishment of 0.013 MU ($p < 0.001$), while prosocial punishment decreases ($-0.004MU, p < 0.05$). This finding indicates that although individuals who act below their own normative convictions punish more often, they refrain from using punishment as a prosocial means to enforce contribution. Rather, they punish more antisocially. Furthermore, contributions are strongly and negatively correlated with normative hubris. That is, those who under-perform with respect to their own norm of contribution contribute less. We find that, like prosociality and risk aversion, holding a strong personal contribution norm is predictive of choosing the certain sanctioning institution. Regression results show that the odds of choosing the uncertain institution decrease by an odds ratio of 0.9 for each additional MU considered appropriate to contribute ($p < .001$; see figure S11 in the SI). While individuals with the lowest contribution norm are estimated to choose the certain sanctioning institution only 34% of the time, individuals with the strongest contribution norm do so 61% of the time. These results support the idea that individuals with strong contribution norms choose the certain institution because of its advantage in enforcing these norms. In contrast, individuals who might want to free-ride according to their low contribution norms may want to use uncertainty to avoid punishment.

Discussion

In reality, uncertainty is likely to be the rule rather than the exception in sanctioning decisions. However, little is known about how it affects the enforcement of cooperation and individuals' attitudes towards it. We used a 5-player public goods experiment with peer punishment in which individuals chose between a certain and an uncertain sanctioning institution repeatedly. In the certain institution, subjects' punishments were

multiplied by a fixed rate, whereas in the uncertain institution their punishments were multiplied by a stochastic factor. We hypothesized that the certain sanctioning institution will be superior in generating social welfare and thus will be preferred by individuals. Our results are consistent with our pre-registered hypotheses: in rounds where subjects chose the certain sanctioning institution, we observe higher contributions to the public good, with less antisocial and total punishment. Thus, prosocial punishment makes up a larger proportion of the already reduced punishment. Since punishment is more directly targeted at free-riders, the smaller amount of punishment is still sufficient to ensure increased compliance with the contribution norm. In contrast, the noise generated by the uncertain institution undermines the prosocial punishment norm and, in turn, hampers the enforcement of the contribution norm. As a result, these factors allow for increased social welfare, with higher payoffs in rounds played in the certain institution making subjects who choose it more often better off. Likely due to experiencing the superiority of the certain institution, our subjects increasingly gravitate towards choosing it over time, making it the majority choice towards the end of the experiment. However, the magnitude of the effect remains limited because the choice of institutions depends to a large extent on individual preferences: a certain institution is more attractive for more risk-averse and prosocial individuals. This may indicate that individuals who plan to free-ride and benefit from reduced norm enforcement efforts deliberately choose the uncertain institution. The results of the effect of subjective contribution norm in our exploratory analysis lend credibility to this interpretation: certain institution choice increases with higher subjective contribution norm. Consequently, individuals with strong preferences may be reluctant to follow through with information about the competitive advantage of certainty.

Our study also sheds light on how punishment behavior is regulated by individuals' differences, motivations and perceptions. Using post-experiment surveys, we found evidence that individuals with higher risk-taking may more likely to engage in prosocial punishment. While the subjective causes and individual differences in punishment and spiteful behavior has been subject to some research [50, 51], a relationship between punishing behavior and risk-taking does not seem to have been noted before. This finding also supports our assumption that risk-seeking individuals value uncertain punishment as more effective, as they not only issue more prosocial punishments, but also prefer the uncertain sanctioning institution.

One of the early theories on causes of punishment posits that humans are strong reciprocators who cooperate and punish non-cooperative behavior [52, 32]. Some recent work has shed some doubts on this hypothesis by showing that prosocial punishment is unrelated to individual contributions [48, 49]. Using survey instruments to infer participants' contribution norms and perceptions, our study sheds further doubt on this hypothesis. While strong reciprocity implies that prosocial punishment should be correlated with individuals' contribution norm, we find no such correlation. Nor do we find a strong relation between prosocial punishment and social value orientation. Furthermore, we find that most prosocial punishment does not originate from individuals with a prosocial motivation, but rather is enacted by individuals with no specific punishment

motives. This finding suggests that many individuals may not punish out of a motivation to establish a prosocial order. However, their punishment is often channeled toward prosocial ends. These findings may suggest that the ultimate cause of punishment is not prosocial incentives, but rather, competitive motivations that may produce prosocial behavior as a result [53].

Our results also indicate that those who deviate from their own contribution norms exhibit more antisocial punishment. This finding, once again, highlights the dark side of human punitive behavior. While our study does not address why this may be the case, it is consistent with the possibility that antisocial punishment can partially result from projecting negative feelings onto others. Besides, we found that humans exhibit a more prosocial representation of their punishing behavior than it is in reality. Moreover, those who overestimate the punishment that they have received, exhibit more antisocial punishment. Besides suggesting that revengeful motivations are among the factors giving rise to antisocial punishment, this finding indicates that those who punish antisocially may perceive their environment to be more hostile. This may be consistent with some past work, relating antisocial punishment with dark personality traits [43, 44, 45].

Materials and Methods

Experimental Procedure

The experiment was conducted online and using Prolific in December 2023. Participants consented to participate in the experiment after they were informed of the aims and overall procedure of the experiment. The experiment was reviewed by the Ethics Committee of the University of Konstanz and received ethics approval (IRB statement 29/2023).

At the beginning of the study, subjects were given 100 monetary units (MU), each worth £0.005. Subjects were divided into groups of 5 and interacted in a public goods game for 25 rounds. In each round, subjects chose between a certain and an uncertain sanctioning institution. Subjects then received an endowment of 10 MU and played a public goods game with subjects in their group who chose the same sanctioning institution, in which they could invest up to 10 MU with a contribution multiplication factor of 2. The fixed factor means that the marginal per capita return (MPCR) depends on the number of players in an institution. Therefore, at first glance, it is more profitable to invest in smaller groups, whereas larger groups may be more attractive for free-riding. However, the expected level of punishment also increases with group size, which counteracts this [10]. The fact that both factors cancel each other out is supported by the fact that the average size of the majority option does not change over the course of the experiment (see SI figure S12). Subsequently, subjects received information about the decisions of their group members and could pay MU to punish other subjects. In the certain sanctioning institution, any MU spent to punish other subjects was multiplied by 3. In the uncertain sanctioning institution, any MU spent to punish other subjects was multiplied by a random real number between 0 and 6. After playing 25 rounds,

subjects completed a 15-decision slider measure of social value orientation task based on Murphy et. al. (2011) [47]. The allocation of a randomly selected decision was paid as a bonus. They also decided on a 5-decision risk preference staircase task based on Falk et. al. (2023) [46] where the final decision was paid out as a bonus. Finally, participants were asked about their punishment strategy, and their perceptions of their own behavior and their subjective contribution norm.

Sample

We conducted our experiment in December 2023 using the oTree framework. We recruited participants from prolific.com, screening for participants with at least 10 previous study submissions and a 95% acceptance rate. Participants received a fixed compensation of £3 and could earn variable bonus payments based on the outcome of the game. The average bonus payment was £1.39. A total of 149 subjects in 30 groups completed the experiment. On average, subjects took approximately 38 minutes to complete the experiment. 40.8% of the subjects identified as female. The four most common countries of origin were South Africa (24%), Portugal (20.8%), Poland (13.6%), and Italy (9.6%). We remove subject rounds that were played as a single player in an institution because players did not make punishment decisions in those rounds. We therefore end up with 3205 subject rounds as observations for analysis.

Analysis

For all round-level analyses, we use multilevel regression models that include group-level and round-level random effects. The use of multilevel regression models is necessary due to the fact that in our experiment subjects play the game in fixed groups in 25 rounds, which may lead to dependencies in the outcome observed in different rounds. To analyze the trend in institution choice by round number, we use logistic regression on institution choice. To assess the effect of institution choice on game performance, we use multilevel linear regression with group-level random intercepts of the individual fraction of choosing the uncertain institution on the final game balance. All models regressing predictors on game behavior, such as contribution, different punishment types, and round payoffs, are multilevel linear regression models with group-level and round-level random intercepts. This is true for the regression models including institution choice, risk preference, social value orientation, perceptions of received and issued punishments, and contribution norms. Welch T-tests were used to compare the round means of game behavior across institutions. To examine the effects of risk preference, social value orientation, punishment motivation, and contribution norm on institution choice, we used multilevel logistic regression with random intercepts at the group and round levels.

To elicit punishment motivation types, we asked participants how much they agreed with the statement that they punished cooperators, free riders, both groups, or indiscriminately. Subjects could indicate their agreement on a 9-point scale ranging from “strongly disagree” to “strongly agree.” Using their responses, we apply k-means cluster analysis and identify two distinct clusters of punishment motivations. While the silhouette width

metric, which indicates the optimal number of clusters, is highest for a five-cluster solution, changes above a two-cluster solution are minimal. For simplicity, we end up with a two cluster solution, with those with a prosocial punishment motivation expressing a mean agreement of 4.78 to punish free-riders, and only values between 1.61 and 1.87 of agreement for the other motivation items. The nonspecific motivation group shows relatively high levels of agreement for all four items, ranging from 3.79 for punishing cooperators to 6.6 for punishing free-riders.

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Figure 1: **Subjects gravitate over time toward the certain sanctioning institution:** Actual (data points) and estimated (fitted line) proportion of subjects choosing the uncertain sanctioning institution by game round. Prediction line yielded by logistic regression model on institution choice. (* = $p < 0.05$; ** = $p < 0.01$; *** = $p < 0.001$).

Figure 2: **Estimated per round means favor the certain sanctioning institution on all indicators of competitive advantage.** Bars represent group- and round-level multilevel model estimation round mean values for contribution, punishment per player in subject's group, antisocial punishment per player in subject's group, and round payoff for each the certain (yellow) and uncertain (green) sanctioning institution with standard error-bars and Welch T-test significance (* = $p < 0.05$; ** = $p < 0.01$; *** = $p < 0.001$)

Figure 3: **Risk-seeking individuals prefer the uncertain institution and use punishment more, while prosocial individuals choose the certain institution and contribute more to the public good.** **A,B:** Multilevel logistic regression estimated probability of choosing the uncertain sanctioning institution by risk preference (A) or Social Value Orientation (B). **C,D:** Regression coefficients and significance of risk preference (C) and social value orientation (D) on contribution, total punishment, and antisocial punishment from linear models with group and round level random effects (* = $p < 0.05$; ** = $p < 0.01$; *** = $p < 0.001$).

Figure 4: **Perceptions of own and received punishment decrease contribution and increase punishment. Subjects with prosocial punishment motivation punish less but more prosocially. Contribution norms increase contribution and decrease antisocial punishment, whereas normative hubris decreases contribution and increases punishment, especially antisocial punishment.** **A,B:** Multi-level linear regression coefficients and significance of perceived own punishment (A) and perceived received punishment (B) on the means of contribution, and total, antisocial, and prosocial punishment. **C:** Boxplots, per round mean values, and Welch T-test significance test results for total, prosocial, and antisocial punishment per player in subject's group for subjects with non-specific (red) and prosocial (blue) punishment motivation. **D:** Regression coefficients and significance of contribution norm and the difference between contribution norm and actual contribution on contribution, and total, prosocial, and antisocial punishment from linear models with group and round level random effects (* = $p < 0.05$; ** = $p < 0.01$; *** = $p < 0.001$)